

WORLD LITERATURE

BIOGRAPHY OF NIZAMI GANJAVI IN THE RESEARCHES OF MİRZA RAHİM FANA

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Abstract

The article studies a document preserved in the personal archive of Mirza Rahim Fana—an Azerbaijani intellectual active in artistic, scholarly, and pedagogical spheres during the late 19th and early 20th centuries—currently kept at the Mahammad Fuzuli Institute of Manuscripts of the Azerbaijan National Academy of Sciences. The material in question is the author's autograph manuscript devoted to exploring the life and literary heritage of the prominent Azerbaijani poet Nizami Ganjavi. Analyzing this manuscript makes it possible to identify the challenges that existed in researching Nizami's biography in Soviet Azerbaijan during the 1920s–1930s. The Nizami-related documents preserved in M. R. Fana's archive further demonstrate that the most trustworthy sources for studying classical figures like Nizami are the autobiographical references embedded in their own works.

Keywords: Mirza Rahim Fana, Nizami Ganjavi, manuscript, personal archive materials, biography.

Introduction.

Nizami Ganjavi (1141–1209) stands as one of the leading figures in Azerbaijani and broader Eastern literary traditions. His global renown largely stems from the “Khamasa,” the five-poem collection composed in Persian between 1174 and 1203. Nizami's literary heritage profoundly influenced not only Persian- and Turkish-language literature across the East but also major European writers such as Dante Alighieri, Giovanni Boccaccio, and William Shakespeare. From the late 17th century onward, his works began to be translated into English, German, French, Italian, and Spanish, resulting in numerous publications that further enhanced his international reputation. By the end of the 19th century, Nizami and his writings became central subjects of scholarly inquiry in Western Europe and Russia, particularly within studies of Persian-language literature. His life and literary legacy have also been extensively investigated in Azerbaijan, although these efforts began comparatively later due to the country's repeated involvement in conflicts. The reason for this is that the country has persistently become a battlefield because it is in the sphere of interest of great empires. The early 20th century marked the first attempts to develop a professional literary historiography in Azerbaijan. Among the pioneering Azerbaijani researchers who examined the heritage of the celebrated poet Nizami Ganjavi was Mirza Rahim Fana (1844–1931).

Brief information about Mirza Rahim Fana.

Rahim Mammadbagir oglu Mirzayev, better known by his pen name Mirza Rahim Fana, was born in Shusha in 1848. He received his initial education at a three-class madrasah in his hometown. Later, he studied the theoretical foundations of poetic art under the prominent Karabakh scholar and teacher, the sage Mirza Abulgasim Ghazi, and at the age of sixteen began composing poetry under the pseudonym “Ashiq.” Gifted with strong organizational abilities, the young Rahim gathered several talented peers in 1862 and formed a small literary circle of three members, with whom he held literary gatherings and creative discussions. Alongside Arabic and Persian, he also mastered

Russian, and between 1866 and 1872 he worked in the civil service of Tsarist Russia in Shusha. From 1872 to 1901, he served as the household keeper at the palace of Khurshidbanu Natavan, daughter of Mehdigulu Khan, the last independent ruler of Karabakh. During this period, he also acted as a secretary of the literary association “Majlisi-uns” (Assembly of Companionship), led by Khan's daughter. In 1901, Fana moved to Baku, where he continued his literary and scholarly pursuits. After Soviet rule was established in Azerbaijan, he became an active participant in the Azerbaijan Literary Society (established in 1925–1927) and contributed to research on the lives and works of Eastern classical authors. He passed away in 1931. [2]

Mirza Rahim Fana's personal archive. Mirza Rahim Fana's personal archive, listed as No. 13 and comprising 62 storage units, is preserved in the collection of the Muhammad Fuzuli Institute of Manuscripts of the Azerbaijan National Academy of Sciences. Among the diverse materials protected in this archive, his research-oriented writings on leading Eastern classical authors—such as Rudaki, Ferdowsi, Nizami, Saadi, Hafez, Fuzuli, and others—hold particular significance. These documents indicate that Persian-language poetry and works composed in the aruz metrical system were being studied in Azerbaijan during the first decade of Soviet rule (1920–1930). Within this archive, the materials devoted to the study of Nizami Ganjavi's life and legacy stand apart from the works produced by Fana's contemporaries on the same topic. As a poet himself, fluent in Persian and deeply knowledgeable about medieval sources, Mirza Rahim Fana approached Nizami studies with a more nuanced perspective. In his research, he compared the information recorded in biographical anthologies (*tazkiras*) with the autobiographical elements found in Nizami's own writings. This method enabled him to reach more precise and reliable conclusions.

Mirza Rahim Fana's researches on Nizami studies. Mirza Rahim Fana undertook extensive research on Nizami's legacy, examining each of the poet's works individually and, when relevant, offering

his own assessments of opinions expressed about Nizami by other notable figures. The researcher documented his analysis of Nizami's works across five notebooks, demonstrating his characteristic meticulousness. Ragub Karimov, who first prepared Fana's works for publication, explains Fana's engagement with Nizami's biography as follows: "*Mirza Rahim's intellectual friends and colleagues, fully aware of his expertise and literary abilities, deemed it essential for him to contribute to this work (the preparation of Nizami's biography) and hoped he would help address a complex issue for his time.*" [3]

The first notebook assembled by M.R. Fana, titled "*Kitabi-Makhzan-al-asrar*," contains 25 pages. On its cover, beneath the heading "*Meanings Intended in the Biography of Sheikh Nizami*" (or "*Points Requiring Clarification in the Biography of Sheikh Nizami Ganjavi*"), Fana outlined a plan to systematically address and interpret the topic.

1. Who is he? Whose son is he? Where is his homeland?
2. What information is there about his birth and death dates, his grave?
3. What do we know about his upbringing and morality, and his profession?
4. What are his religious and philosophical views and what are his main works? [4]

M.R. Fana approached his research with great diligence, emphasizing the importance of referring to Nizami's own works to obtain the most reliable information about the poet: "*The most reliable source about the Sheikh is his own works. From here, one can obtain information about both his personality and the date of writing of his works*" [4]. In his article "*Kitabi-Makhzan-al-asrar*," Fana analyzes Nizami's *The Treasure House of Mysteries*, referring to it as a "treasure of truth." He observes that each section of *Makhzan-al-asrar* provides valuable insights for readers. Notably, this work consists of 20 articles, each accompanied by a story that illustrates and reinforces the moral-philosophical concept presented in the corresponding article. Fana further notes that the other four poems in Nizami's *Khamsa*—*Khosrow and Shirin*, *Layla and Majnun*, *Seven Beauties*, and *Iskandarnamah*—depict events of human life, thereby offering readers guidance on the world and the principles governing it. From this perspective, the entire *Khamsa* can be understood as a comprehensive treatise aimed at the cultivation of moral understanding. In essence, Nizami elaborated on the moral-philosophical concepts introduced in *The Treasure House of Mysteries* through illustrative examples in his other poems.

M.R. Fana concluded that Nizami, the subject of his research, possessed exemplary moral character. This conclusion was based on the assessments of Nizami by his contemporaries and later followers, some of which Fana highlighted in his work. Under the section titled "*On the Virtue of Sheikh Nizami*," he presented examples from various poets: one verse by Jalaluddin Rumi, two by Hafez Shirazi, one by Mektebi Shirazi, one by Vusal Shirazi, eight by Abdurrahman Jami, twelve by Vahshi Kirmani, two by Muhammad Fuzuli, and one by Alisher Navoi. As an example, Fana

cites a verse from a ghazal by Hafez:

چو سلک در خو شایست نظم تو حافظ گه گاه لطف سبق میبرد
ز نظم نظامی

Which can be translated as: "*How pleasant your poetry is, Hafez, for you have learned the lesson of order from Nizami's works*" [4].

Mirza Rahim Fana as one of the first biographers of Nizami Ganjavi. M.R. Fana attempted to restore the poet's biography. He determines the date of birth and death of Sheikh Nizami based on the information provided by the prominent orientalist Huseyn Danish (1870-1943) and compares this information with another source, the encyclopedic source called "*Buaqkha*": "*In his book about Persian writers, Huseyn Danish wrote that the Sheikh was born in 535 AH, corresponding to 1140-41 AD, and died in 599 AH, corresponding to 1199 AD. In "Lughati-umumiye-Buaqkha" it is written that he was born in 1140-41 and died in 1203 AD. According to these two sources, the Sheikh's life span is not 63 years, but 64 years, which is consistent with what the Sheikh himself said.*" (Huseyn Danish, in his book about Persian-speaking literary figures, gives the Sheikh's birth date as 535 AH with the AH date.) This makes it 1140-1141 AD. He wrote the date of the poet's death as 599 AH, that is, 1199 AD. However, in the encyclopedic reference book "*Buaqkha*", the date of the Sheikh's death is written as 1203 AD. According to both sources, the poet lived a total of 63 years. This information is consistent with the autobiographical notes in the poet's works.) [4].

M.R. Fana writes that there is no information about Nizami's childhood and youth, upbringing and education. He blames historians for this. In his opinion, classical historians were not inclined to write world events, but preferred writing only stories of murder, robbery, and quarrels. Therefore, the author was disappointed that he could not find a reliable source on this subject. Fana, after these notes, determines where and from whom Nizami received his education not based on facts, but on his own logic. Based on the logic that other famous Azerbaijani poets who were contemporaries of the poet - Khagani Shirvani (1121-1199), Falaki Shirvani (first half of the 12th century), Zulfigar Shirvani (1190-1291) and others reached perfection thanks to the meliku-shuara (master of poets) of their time, Abul-Ula Ganjavi (11th century), he assumes that Nizami could also learn from him. He expresses his opinion as follows: "*Sheikh Nizami may have acquired knowledge in the presence of the aforementioned master, and there is no information about whether he was educated in Azerbaijan or Iran.*" (Sheikh Nizami could also have learned science in the presence of the master mentioned above. Thus, there is no information about who his master was in Azerbaijan or Iran) [4].

M.R. Fana also touches on the issue of Nizami's nationality and literary identity. He specifically notes that Nizami was born and raised in Ganja, and spent his entire life in this city. The scholar states that considering that he was born and lived in a region where the population spoke Turkish, that is, his circle of influence consisted of Turks, Nizami also spoke Turkish and adhered to Turkish customs and traditions. This led to the fact that, despite the fact that the language of his works

was Persian, the influence of the Turkish language and Turkish customs and traditions were sometimes felt in "Khamisa". In general, M.R. Fana, who is an admirer of Nizami's works, highly appreciates the poet's artistic world. The scholar proudly notes that Nizami was a supernaturally creative person, a deeply thoughtful philosopher-poet. He wants to convey Nizami's prodigy to the readers by giving numerous examples from "Khamisa": "*The Sheikh's poems, written with masterful skill in a refined literary style and imbued with a musical quality, also carry profound meaning. Through the depiction of various events and the artistic expression of different states of the human soul, the poet's works have served for centuries as a source of great spiritual and aesthetic pleasure.*" [4].

M.R. Fana, an enthusiast and connoisseur of classical Eastern literature, tried to determine the place and position of the great Nizami in the entire Eastern world under the title "Summary of Sheikh Nizami's Life and Legacy" (A Brief Overview of Sheikh Nizami's Literary Position). He tried to evaluate Nizami's legacy in comparison with other Eastern classics, his predecessors and successors. He stated that Nizami holds a special place in the background of the works of poets such as Ferdowsi, Anvari and Saadi. He notes that just as Nizami respectfully remembered and praised his predecessors Ferdowsi and Khagani, the great poets of the East who came after Nizami, Jalaluddin Rumi, Hafez Shirazi, Abdurrahman Jami, Alisher Navoi, Muhammad Fuzuli and others, also respected him and described him in the most beautiful expressions. [4].

Conclusion. Among the materials on Nizami Ganjavi preserved in M.R. Fana's personal archive, the study entitled "Meanings Intended in the Biography of Sheikh Nizami" (*Points Requiring Clarification in the*

Biography of Sheikh Nizami Ganjavi) is of particular importance. This work is one of the important examples of the first stage of Azerbaijani Nizami studies. This article allows us to obtain information about how searches were conducted in Soviet Azerbaijan at the beginning of the 20th century to clarify the dates of Nizami's birth and death, and to determine the literary environment in which the poet lived and worked. The assessment of Nizami's legacy in this study in the background of the works of his predecessors, contemporaries and successors can be assessed as M.R. Fana's contribution to Nizami studies. The inclusion of verses about the poet, whom the followers of the Nizami literary school considered their sage, in the study indicates both the love of the author of the study for his research object and the high appreciation given to Nizami by important figures of Eastern literature.

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